

FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR OF MONOTONICALLY AND FATIGUE LOADED CLAY-EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: This work investigates the fracture mechanism and modes of failure of an epoxy resin with a dispersion of modified layered silicates in the polymer matrix. A single load and repetitive load were applied to these clay-epoxy materials and the fracture behaviour of the failed materials was studied. Clay-epoxy nanocomposites were successfully synthesized with a commercially available 1-Methylimidazole curing agent. The morphology of these materials was investigated by XRD and TEM. The findings demonstrated a pattern of clay morphology typically found in nanocomposite systems. The fractured materials were examined using an E-SEM. The appearance of the epoxy and the clay-epoxy fracture surfaces from the monotonically loaded samples were different. The micro observations of the epoxy and the clay-epoxy fracture surfaces from the fatigue loaded samples showed different patterns. In conclusion, the addition of silicate as well as the type of loading strongly determine the fracture mechanism and the modes of failure.

KEYWORDS: layered silicates, epoxy, four-point loading test, fatigue test, mode of failure.

INTRODUCTION

Polymer nanocomposites filled with layered silicates have been studied extensively in the last decade because of the dramatic improvement in their performance with a silicate addition only of 5wt% or less [1-4]. Montmorillonite or MMT, one of the common silicates, is a crystalline, 2:1 layered clay mineral in which a central alumina octahedral layer is sandwiched between two silica tetrahedral layers [5]. The layers are separated by a regular spacing, which is commonly termed the gallery. The more expanded this gallery distance, the better the properties of clay-polymer nanocomposites, because the polymer matrix has intruded to a greater extent into the filler.

The basic principle of polymer nanocomposite synthesis is that the polymer or its monomer is able to move in and react within the inter layer galleries of the layered silicate. In order to achieve this penetration, the layered silicate has to have an organophilic surface treatment through a cation exchange reaction in the gallery. When the nature and polarity of the layered silicate gallery is similar to that of the resin and the hardener, the molecules will intercalate into the gallery. A thermodynamic equilibrium between the surface energy of the layered silicate and the polarity of the swelling monomers determines the intercalation process. The curing process in the galleries changes this equilibrium and enables further reactive monomers to diffuse into the gallery. This dispersion process results in the increase of the

gallery distance. It is well known that a balance between the intergallery and extragallery polymerization rate is essential to achieve intercalation and subsequent exfoliation [1]. Therefore, the nature of the curing agent, as well as the curing condition, or vice versa the chain formation mechanism, play important roles in the clay dispersion in the epoxy resin [6].

Two types of polymer nanocomposite structures can be obtained, namely intercalated and exfoliated structures. Intercalated structures are formed when a small increase of the gallery distance occurs. On the other hand, exfoliated structures are formed when the silicate layers are well separated and individually dispersed in the polymer matrix. Since the latter structure is more homogeneous than the former, exfoliated nanocomposites exhibit better properties. However, it is difficult to obtain an exfoliated structure by itself. In fact the majority of the studies show that polymer nanocomposites possess mixed structures or an intercalated structure only [7]. That is, exfoliation rarely seems to occur completely.

It is reported that the modulus, strength and toughness of different types of clay-epoxy systems improve significantly for the addition of 5wt% clay [8, 9]. However, the study of fracture mechanism and modes of failure of fatigue loaded nanocomposites has not been examined. In the present study, the fracture mechanism and modes of failure of epoxy and clay-epoxy materials will be investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The material used in the present work was Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A / DGEBA resin (Araldite Algy 9708-1) purchased from Ciba-Geigy combined with 1-Methylimidazole (1-MI), purchased from Aldrich, as the curing agent. The filler, which is a commercial MMT, Nanomer I.30E, was purchased from Nanocor Inc.

Preparation of Materials

The epoxy and clay powder were dried overnight at 50 °C in a vacuum prior to sample production. Unfilled epoxy specimens were made by mixing the epoxy resin and 2.5 wt% hardener and then blending them in a SpeedMixer at 3000 rpm for 1 min. Filled specimens were synthesized by mixing the desired amount of clay with epoxy resin at $(76 \pm 1)^\circ\text{C}$ using an overhead stirrer for 30 min; 2.5 wt% of hardener was then added into the mixture and mixed in the SpeedMixer at 3000 rpm for 1 min. The blend was poured into release-agent-coated-aluminum moulds with mylar-sheet-covered glass bases, then cured at 160 °C for 2 hrs, and followed by a post-cure at 180 °C for 2 hrs.

This study involved two specimen configurations. Firstly, a window frame mould with dimensions of 150 mm x 150 mm and thickness of 3 mm was prepared. The square plate material was then machined, producing specimens with dimensions of 50 mm x 25 mm x 2 mm. These rectangular samples were used for four-point loading tests. Secondly, triangular moulds with a thickness of 4 mm were specially designed to manufacture fatigue samples. The triangular samples were ground using sand paper of 180 grid followed by 1200 grid, to obtain a homogeneous thickness of 3 mm. These triangular samples were used for fatigue tests.

Characterization of Nanocomposites

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed using a Phillips PW 1130 generator which was equipped with Traces software. A voltage of 40kV and current of 25mA were employed for Cu K α radiation. Measurements were performed in a range of $2\theta = 1^\circ - 30^\circ$ for the unfilled and filled epoxy samples as well as the dried MMT powder.

Transmission electron microscope samples were cut using a Leica Reichert Ultracut S Microtome with a Diatome diamond knife, which was placed at an angle of 6° . The 70 nm thickness of sections were collected on hexagonal 300 mesh copper grids. The images were obtained from a Phillips EM 420 Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM), which was operated in bright field mode at 100 kV.

The monotonically loaded samples were obtained from a four-point loading test. The four-point loading tests were carried out at ambient temperature on an INSTRON 4505, which was equipped with Merlin software. The machine was operated at a rate of 0.85 mm/min and a 1 kN load cell was applied. This test was conducted based on the ASTM D 790M-86 Standard.

The fatigue loaded samples were obtained from a fatigue test. The fatigue tests were carried out at ambient temperature, using a cantilever-bending machine, operating at 24 Hz.

Fracture surfaces were observed using an Environmental - Scanning Electron Microscope (E-SEM) FEI Quanta 200. This microscope was operated at 20 kV at a low vacuum mode and equipped with EDX apparatus.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MMT epoxy based nanocomposites were successfully synthesized by in-situ polymerisation. Four different clay loadings; 2.5wt%, 5wt%, 7.5wt%, and 10wt%, were prepared to produce the MMT-epoxy systems.

The structures of the specimens were examined by XRD and TEM. The results show a typical pattern of clay-epoxy nanocomposites, shown in Figures 1 and 2 for XRD and TEM observations respectively. Figure 1(a) is a powder diffractogram of pure MMT, showing a strong peak due to (001) corresponding to a d-spacing of 2.2 nm, with the (002) and (101) peaks also quite evident. For the DGEBA nanocomposites only a very slight (001) peak can be observed indicating that this system is largely exfoliated for all clay contents. Even though there is no (001) peak, it is clear that the (101) peak can be observed and its intensity increases with the clay content. This shows that XRD can detect the presence of the organoclay.

Figure 2 shows the TEM micrographs of 2.5wt% MMT-epoxy nanocomposites. These images exhibit a number of parallel organoclay layers. It was calculated that the average layer distance lied between 4.2 – 11.1 nm for all clay contents and a minimum layer distance of 2.5 nm. This indicates that these materials possess a mixed structure of exfoliated and intercalated structures, where exfoliation is at best partial.

(a)

Fig. 1: XRD patterns of (a) MMT and (b) epoxy and MMT–epoxy nanocomposites

Fig. 2: TEM micrographs of 2.5wt% MMT–epoxy nanocomposites

Micro observations of the epoxy and MMT–epoxy fracture surfaces of monotonically loaded samples can be seen in Figure 3. Figure 3(a) demonstrates river-marking lines of the epoxy

fracture surface. These river-marking lines show the propagation of cracks, which started from a defect in the sample. This pattern disappeared when clay particles were added. The pattern of the fracture surface of the MMT–epoxy is different to that of the pristine material. The fracture surfaces of the filled specimens show a hackle pattern and the direction of these hackle patterns indicates the propagation of the cracks, as shown in Figure 3(b). Similar to the pristine material, the crack started from a defect. It was suggested that the fracture mechanism changed from a brittle failure to a mixed crack, which is a combination between a brittle crack and shear deformation. However, the fracture surfaces of the filled epoxy exhibit some small and big clumps. From EDX measurement, these clumps contain high clay particle concentrations compared to other parts without clumps. These images indicate that some organoclay particles did not exfoliate as expected, but they formed aggregates with different sizes. This suggests that the clumps are related to the aggregate-filled systems [10, 11].

Fig. 3: E-SEM images of fracture surface of monotonically loaded samples of (a) epoxy and (b) 2.5wt% MMT-epoxy

Micro observations of the epoxy and MMT–epoxy fracture surfaces of fatigue loaded samples can be seen in Figure 4. Figure 4(a) demonstrates river marking lines of the epoxy fracture surface. The river marking lines are identified as striations for fatigue loaded samples [12]. The striations occurred due to the fast repetitive load on the materials. With a thorough examination the striations were close together on the edge of the fracture surface and further apart on the center part of the fracture surface. Moreover, it could be seen that the crack started from the edge of the samples and propagated to the center part of the samples. Comparing Figures 3(a) and 4(a), the river marking lines of the monotonically loaded samples are bumpier than the striations of the fatigue loaded samples. The pattern of the fracture surface of fatigue loaded samples of MMT–epoxy is different to that of the pristine material, as shown in Figure 4(b). On the MMT-epoxy fracture surfaces of the fatigue loaded samples, indistinct striations and an indistinct hackle pattern were observed. Comparing Figures 3(b) and 4(b) as examples, the striations of the fatigue loaded samples generally had flat profiles and a smaller number of hackle markings.

Fig. 4: E-SEM images of fracture surface of fatigue loaded samples of (a) epoxy and (b) 2.5wt% MMT-epoxy

CONCLUSIONS

An aggregate-intercalated-exfoliated structure is formed in the MMT-epoxy nanocomposites. The clay addition changes the mechanism of failure from a fracture pattern typical of brittle epoxy materials to a mixed crack, which is a combination between a brittle crack and shear deformation. In the filled epoxy, crack propagation is formed by multiple shear deformation of the matrix where the stress is concentrated in the hackles around the aggregates. The crack branches propagate along the hackle direction.

The fracture surfaces of the monotonically loaded unfilled epoxy samples show a river marking line pattern, whereas the fracture surfaces of the fatigue loaded unfilled epoxy samples show a striation pattern.

The fracture surfaces of the monotonically loaded filled epoxy samples show a hackle pattern and a few river marking lines, whereas the fracture surfaces of the fatigue loaded filled epoxy samples show a few striations and an indistinct hackle pattern.

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